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Old Town's Urban Transformation and Immovable Cultural Heritage in Cityscape

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Towns are being explored by scientists of various disciplines, as various interests and processes influencing one another intertwine in this live structure. Structure of towns constantly changes, i.e. old urban formations are replaced and supplemented with new ones under favourable economic conditions also all of them may be destroyed physically or by nature cataclysms. Such changes (transformations) change previous structure of towns, cityscape even totally new shape may be assumed.

All towns are different and oddly unique as different utopian ideas of philosophers, artists and engineers had great influence on origin and structure of towns. However, not all of us assess this remained immovable heritage, which reflects culture of appropriate civilisations, equally.

Ideologies of different stages about urban planning and correspondence of such utopian thoughts in the structure of modern-day old town were analysed in this scientific article. Urban transformations that took place and influence of remained immovable cultural heritage on cityscape were reviewed.

Keywords: urban transformation, immovable cultural heritage, cityscape, environmental management.

Introduction

As it is possible decide from the history, town is a point of maximum social power and cultural concentration. Historians agreed, that first forms of villages, that slightly reminds future town, can be detected even in Palaeolithic culture, i.e. the Old Stone Age, but it is necessary to mention that its only tentative references to future human urban life. Approximately 12 thousand year ago, small groups of nomads, i.e. rovers, acquired a possibility to live in one place more constantly, as they started to engage in agriculture. Therefore, while main source of human subsistence was hunting and fishing, they could not even thought about settled way of life.

The way we define a town, depends of the view, we refer to. Historians shall explain its circumstances in one way, anthropologists in other way and the economists otherwise. Economically, a town is a place, where people are engaged in business and trade, but not in agriculture (Samalavičius, 2008).

It is possible to imagine, that, at that time, a place chosen according to appropriate natural priorities in the course of time was changed in accordance with needs of society, thus reforming steady natural landscape. Villages were formed by cutting trees, farming, building and constant use of ridges, and, in the process of time as well as after plenty of buildings were thickened, unique cityscapes were formed.

Historical centres of towns distinguish by variety of image and urban space, acquired within century-long process of urban structures of town. Distinction and visual uniqueness of town are very important in new globalisation era, as they are components of cultural identity. In summarising components of urban structure, one can notice, that the most stable component, that changes the less, is street network. (Dijokienė, 2009).

As specialists state, landscape and especially cityscape are realised not only as a place, where (national or other) identity may be created or retained, but also as a system of values or a very complicated discourse – a language, where many economical, social and cultural concepts are encoded. (Čepaitienė, 2008).

Since anthropogenic environment created by human constantly changes, so if not protecting primary development layers, this multifunctional and immovable cultural heritage significant for recognition of civilization will simply disappear and will not leave any signs for prospective active minds.

This article is more of survey nature, exploring details of past and nowadays cityscape and defining goals for further scientific researches, which may be accented to application of remained objects for further use as well as their application to modernising environment. The article contains many historical illustrations and facts therefore it must be cognitive as well. Publication is presented in international English language so that not only Lithuanian but also scientists from other countries could familiarise with development of this town.

Aim of the research: to analyse urban development of Klaipėda Old town, compare it with famous ideologies and utopias of early philosophers and urban planners. To present photo fixation of different periods and compare transformations of buildings that took place. To present conclusions how remained (or non-existent) immovable cultural heritage influence cityscape and what should be improved in anthropogenic planning in order the Old town would be socially enliven.

Methods of the research: analysis and summarising of scientific and historical articles as well as literature, analysis and portrait of geographical data and comparison of photo fixations.

Subject of the research: Klaipėda city Old town (Lithuania's port), which during its history was affected not only by usual physical and natural factors, but by different cultures as well.

Geography and history of our country has no such written monuments about Lithuania, which ancient Babylonia, China, India are proud of, having chronicles dated several thousand year, which contain much information about nature, landscape and life of that time. There is no doubt, that here (in Lithuania – author) past of geographical perception was interesting and rich as well. Archaeological findings and verbal monuments are evidences of that. Illustrations as well as drawings of terrains, plans and various schemes are considered as the oldest cultural monuments. Claudius Ptolemy, famous Roman astronomer and geographer of Greco origin, among his other maps also made a map of Central Europe, where the Baltic, Neman and Baltic tribes were shown (Fig. 1-2). Archaeological digs, during which Roman coins were found, show that ancient Greeks and Romans visited our country (coast), that sailing by Baltic Sea stopped here to buy amber, fur, wax or honey (Krupickas, 2000).

Germs of Lithuanian port started from small village of Curonian fishers near Danė river. In 1252 a castle were built and an establishment of the town was provided. In 1257 rights of Lübeck town were provided to Klaipėda, thus legally it became a city. Klaipėda is the oldest German settlement in Eastern Prussia, besides the oldest city in current Lithuania having city rights. Klaipėda was built according to Roman town-military camp model: everything served for military purposes. Stone buildings were also forbidden, so that in case of attack the town would be burned (KMI, 2009).

Horizontal layout of Klaipėda old town

Fig. 1–2

Fragments of Central Europe maps by C. Ptolemy, where coasts of Lithuanian territory are shown (Samalavičius, 2008)

The city was totally destroyed during attack of Lithuanians in 1323 and in 1409 building of the town, its strengthening with banks and towers was started again. In 1525, when Prussia became a worldly state, Klaipėda city started to develop and increase. Both old suburbs of Vitė and Smeltė as well as new suburb to the south from the old Danė river channel, later named as Friedrich suburb, expanded (Fig. 3-4 (Klaipėdos...2012)).

M. Brazauskas in his scientific article about Klaipėda cultural layers (...2008) presented much information about performed archaeological researches and facts about initial development of Klaipėda. According to the author, archaeological researches of Klaipėda Old town lasted for several decades and accumulated archaeological material enforced reconsider development of the city. Initial development in Klaipėda Old town is averagely fixed at the sea level and above, and the oldest cultural layers lie averagely at the depth of 2.5-3.0 meters from current land surface. It should be added, that the city experienced 4 large fires (in 1520, 1540, 1678, 1854), which had great influence on the development of the city. The city, set after its last fire, practically formed current level of Klaipėda surface. Prohibition to build stone buildings expired after the fire in 1678 in Klaipėda. Earliest foundations of the buildings, dated XVII century were found on the land plot at Tiltų str. 6. Paving of the streets in the Old town was started only at XVIII century: about year 1720 it was indicated that each citizen must pave 10 feet of the street around its house and the remained part of streets and markets must be paved by town's treasury.

On 28 October 1996 Klaipėda Old town was included into List of Urban Places of the Register of Immovable Cultural Values and boundaries of the territory were defined (Klaipėdos...2012).

Fig. 3–4

Klaipėda city plans. Appropriate development in 1630 and in 1650 (Special plan of Klaipėda old town (2012))

Since archaeologists found traces of Greek and Roman visits at this coast, so it is interesting to explore, how they imagined an ideal town and if these ideologies correspond to layout of Klaipėda Old city.

We could decide about how the ancient Romans realised ideally planned town from the only remained tractate, intended for architecture of that time "*De Architectura Libri Decem*" (Ten books about architecture), belonging to Vitruvius pen. Vitruvius was not interested in social issues very much, but it was written that market square should occur in the town centre, but if a port will be established, the market square should be moved closer to the port. The town should have been surrounded by circle form wall, fortified with towers. By following behests of Hippocrates, Vitruvius cared about, that climate conditions in the town would be hygienic. Layout of circle form 8 dominant wind directions should have been regulated by 8 streets crossing these directions. Number 8 was selected because of old magic or religious reasons. In all probability, Vitruvius, like Plato, selected circle plan with the intention that circle form will satisfy requirements of harmony, regularity and closure (Fig. 5-6).

Fig. 5-6

Ideal plans of the town by Vitruvius (Samalavičius, 2008)

One of the most typical features of Roman town was architecture of two main streets: *cardo* led to north and *decumannus* led to east and west. Main streets of the Roman town crossed in the town centre, where natural place for main public space, i.e. forum, of the town was. The other Roman architect Hygen explained, that ideal town should not be larger than 2.4 thousand feet (~700 m - author) of length and 1.6 thousand feet (~500 m - author) of width, otherwise longer distances would rather harden audibility of alarms. Tractate of Vitruvius would hardly be related with a tradition of utopian thinking and planning. As it was already mentioned, he was not interested in public development and social issues. It was a plan, intended for satisfaction of requirements of formal structure (Samalavičius, 2008).

At XV century, intense theoretical searches of ideal town took place. Planners of renaissance towns saturated geometry and mathematics, reflections of which envisaged in theory and practise of construction of Roman Republic and wished to apply for their era. All great Renaissance architects (Antonio Filarete (1400–1469), Leone Alberti (1404–1472), Fra Giovanni Giocondo (1434–1515), Francesco di Giorgio (1439–1502), Leonardo da Vinci (1452–1519) and Andrea Palladio (1518–1580) started works of designing of ideal towns. They concerned about place and establishment of the town in good agricultural or strategic region. They recommended qualification of streets, safety and expenses, layout of spaces for gardens, recreation and public needs, systems of elimination of storm after-effects and waste removal as well as water supply, zones for industry and crafts as well as usage of modules and proportions for streets, entries and bunkers. Da Vinci was even

more progressive: he was actively interested in public health and a need to equip streets of several levels. Also Da Vinci presented recommendations for number of citizens: there should not be more than 30 thousand citizens and about 5 thousand houses built within all town.

Rationality of planning during Renaissance period was stimulated by many factors, not only by new military technique and development of mathematics. Euclidean geometry and Ptolemy astronomy also had influence on it. Namely Euclidean geometry, being especially logically consistent, stimulated minds of Renaissance to develop searches of order. Projects of ideal towns created by them reminded crystals of ordered configuration with strict internal system of circles, corners, squares and pentagons. Every building in the town: halls, chapels, public and residential buildings, were situated especially accurately and precisely.

Scamozzi in his work "An idea of universal architecture" unsuccessfully tried propagate an ideal town plan (Fig. 7), explaining, that he concerns not only about how to create defensive system,

Fig. 7

Ideal town plan by V. Scamozzio in 1516 (Samalavičius, 2008)

Fig. 8

G. Ideal town plan by Vasari in 1550

but a model piece of art. A project of architect, biographer and artist Giorgio Vasari (Fig. 8) surpassed this model). We can see here octagonal plan with a field inside it, surrounded by round and angular fields. It is a creation of Renaissance military needs and new aesthetics of the town. There was a square for military parades inside and not a market square. Ways from this square led to defensive bunkers at town borders (Samalavičius, 2008).

Since special plan of Klaipėda Old town's Immovable cultural heritage protection involves very large territory (Ill. 9 marked with yellow colour), but considering to historical literature, a wish occur to divide the old town of the port into three parts according to stages of its development (Fig. 9). Division may be marked in the plan according to parts A, B and C, accordingly marking boundaries with red, green and yellow colours. According to currently available archaeological data Scientists state, that current Old town of Klaipėda is not in its real (natural) place, but the article analyse exactly this place, which may be identified according to existing cartographical material (Fig. 9 marked with red colour).

Fig. 9

Partition of Klaipėda Old town according to stages of development

Scientists, who researched and described development of Klaipėda earlier, state that the town was formed around current Tiltų and Turgaus streets (Fig. 9, marked with brown colour). Therefore, there are no firm evidences in which place initial port was. In New Danė river watercourse, this place can be found in cartographic plans, which is marked as cargo transshipment scales (Fig. 4).

Main square i.e. *forum*, does not correspond to cross centre of main streets, it is also more likely near the site of an ancient castle than contemporary port, but system of streets were really designed according to mathematical principles, as this system is of geometrically regular forms (Fig. 10). So called micro quarters are of 50–60 m length and 20–40 m width. When looking at highlighted system of streets, we can guess if some sections of streets were not destroyed in the course of time. Such sections would make this system more thicken and it would become more accurate and symmetric. Number of highlighted streets is even (12) also classification of streets according to activity of industrialists and craftsmen remained.

Length of the Old town is about 600 meters and width about 250 metres, and that is one more indicator which corresponds to requirements raised for planning of that year ideal towns. From performed functional zoning in accordance with objective purpose of land usage (Lithuanian ...2008), from orthographical material it could be seen where lands of residential and commercial purpose (Fig. 10, marked with cinnamon colour) and public, recreational purpose (Fig. 10, marked with green colour) locate. All area constitutes about 14 ha, 4 ha from them of public space, 1 ha – engineering systems and 9 ha land plot of residential and commercial purpose. Solid layout of the land shall negatively affect urban citizens. Layout of exploratory territory is dense (71 %), but layout of public spaces and plenty of green areas spread within all territory show that health and well being of citizens were cared about.

It is necessary to emphasise that in the middle of 17 century lack of land occurred because of increasing number of citizens, therefore the old stream channel of Danė river was filled up, which separated the old town from Friedrich suburb. This wash approximately corresponds to current street named Didžioji vandens (Fig. 9, marked with blue colour). It was the start of further urban development and disjuncture from then Friedrich suburb was abolished (Fig. 9, marked with green colour).

Fig. 10

Layout of streets and functional zoning

Visual changes of buildings and immovable cultural heritage

Often heritage constitutes background of cultural identity of a society. However, every part of the society and every generation individually understand cultural value and goals of treatment with it. Material objects created by foretime people shall become a heritage only then, when we select important for us things. By deciding what was valuable in the past and by selecting manifestations of representation of the past in nowadays, we shall solve not abstract aesthetic, but essential ideological and political problems (Jurevičienė, 2010).

It is considered that heritage is very closely related both to people and their identity and to residential place of people. It was offered to divide heritage objects into seven categories: nature, landscape, monuments, artefacts, activity, people and places (Ashworth G, 2008).

Landscape would be the most suitable category for researches according to theme of article. However, this concept consists of many objects, especially if one goes deep in cultural landscape. Therefore it is purposeful to narrow exploratory environment and criteria, focusing to cityscape. Namely the old cityscape is affected mostly by expansion of urban boundaries and thickening of layout. The further the clearer skyscrapers and other vitreous buildings of modern forms can be seen in cityscape and offered by globalisation processes. Low-rise buildings (often old towns) could not be seen in such panorama when looking to town. All new buildings are similar by their architectural or social ideas to an international extent, but at the same moment, quaintly, compete one with other (especially by its highness and memorable architectural form).

Unique objects of architectural heritage in the town shall always distinguish by active self-communication, as they are branded in memory of townspeople, arise emotional and semantic associations. Each person has a map of town in his/her head: landmarks, paths, outskirts, districts and one need to agree, that new radical architectural interventions shall destroy psychological place

perception of townsman. Given high rate of life and change of values, a society must periodically reorient to variable nature of activity, modified spatial encirclement and semiotic or functional conversion in their surrounding space (Rudokas K, 2013). Towns are expanding supplementing by new objects, which shall change former identities of cityscape.

In order to retain initial features of town's layout, it is necessary to systematically plan and implement urban development. Construction of high buildings in towns should be considered well, as they change many social and economical interests and, of course, affect well-established cityscape. The old urban structure could not be affected by such buildings. With high buildings it would be purposeful to awake outlying terrains, which are far from old town, but potential to complex development. Low-rise visual identity of layout of particular features is typical to old towns, such territories must be protected from architectural high neologisms and to refresh social activeness (by forming as different as possible functional activity), by strengthening cultural uniqueness.

Urban-based transformations in cityscape shall take place at different rate, considering many factors. Elements of cityscape in appropriate place may vary within 2 – 5, 10 -100 or other yearly intervals. It is less likely, that elements of cityscape would not change totally for 200 or more years.

Turgaus street (Fig. 11–12) is one of pivotal streets of Klaipėda Old town, according to which a town was formed. Looking to photo fixations of different periods, one can compare what has changed within 75 years. Width of the street remained the same, cobbly and pedestrian paths on the sides are separated from carriageway by green vegetation. Buildings are situated along the street, integrity is felt. Highness of the layout remained unchanged. On the right side of the street facades of the buildings were changed, form and number of windows also changed. The salient difference is that construction of religious purpose in the distance did not remain. When comparing this existing/non existing detail at the contour of cityscape, its shortage is felt. Monotony in highness of buildings and in the distance of oriental object is felt because of this shortage of building of cultural purpose. In summarising these photo fixations, it is possible to assess that cityscape has changed in 1 important detail.

Facade of the hotel in Žvejų street (Fig. 13–14) has changed because of changed entrance into building and additional details (premises) on the top floor. Width and covering of the street remained and integrity and highness of layout on the right side has not changed as well. On the right side of the street number of buildings increased and they already had details of modernisation (wide glassy windows). Many discussions may occur because of occurrence of these buildings and their facade appearance as in this place, alongside with old forms, a building full of glassy details was inserted. In summarising these photo fixations a change in detail 1 was also noted.

Facade features of an exploratory building on the other axial street of Klaipėda Old town (Tiltų str.) (Fig. 15–16) has changed within 85 years only because of public passage that was remade from premises on the first floor of the building. Such change is felt more in functionality of the building on behalf of townspeople, but not for general feature of cityscape. Covering of the street remained

Fig. 11–12

Turgaus str. in 1937 and 2012 (prepared using interactive maps and information from thematic forums)

Fig. 13–14

Hotel in Žvejų str.
(prepared using
interactive maps and
information from
thematic forums)

as in all old town, highness of buildings remained as well, but a building on the right side does not exist anymore. There are no objects of modern construction instead of it, influencing cityscape. Changes may be assessed by 1.

Also it is necessary to review changes in that time *forum* or in current Theatre square. Difference of period of photo fixations is 112 years. It is very hard to state unambiguously because of the change in size of public space itself. Highness of buildings as well as covering of the street did not change. Details of modern architecture are seen again on the right side (plenty of glass on the facade). Occurrence of flora is also noted, and above it, in the distance, new rectangular building can be observed. Number of more significant changes is minimal – 1.

For variety of the research, a terrain from beyond the river (Danė (Dangė)), C part of the Old town, according to division (Fig. 9, yellow line), was taken. During gathering data for article, it became clear that this particular terrain is subject to changes, and knowing plans of current town's politicians, significant urban transformation will be made to this terrain, which will change current cityscape. Width of Danės str. (Fig. 19–22) did not change, but layout has changed significantly. Public space of recreational purpose is situated on the right side of the street (Fig. 19–20) instead of former buildings (Biržos building). Therefore the view overlooks to the river and A part of the Old town. Former densely developed street shall become a cognitive place, where space can be felt, but not a narrow

Fig. 15–16

Former building of
penny-bank in 1927 in
F. Wilhelm str. and in
2012 (Tiltų str.) (prepared
using interactive maps
and information from
thematic forums)

Fig. 17–18

Forum in 1900 and
Theatre square in
2012 (prepared using
interactive maps and
information from
thematic forums)

Fig. 19–20

A building of administration purpose in Danés str. (prepared using interactive maps and information from thematic forums)

Fig. 21–22

Danés str. In 1910 and 2012 (prepared using interactive maps and information from thematic forums)

corridor between buildings. Also there are no buildings remained on the left side of the street, instead of which today public (social, recreational) space exists. Two obvious changes, which have great influence on cityscape, can be seen from this side of observation (assessment).

When looking at the same place (building) from the other direction of the street (Fig. 21–22), other changes can be observed that took place within one hundred years. Covering of the street has changed and even metal rails, embedded into carriageway, can be observed. Today they do not exist. Also significant changes can be observed in highness of the buildings. Two new high and modern buildings in the central part over the building can be observed. High building can also be seen on the right side and on the left side modern (glassy) buildings exists. As we can see, when looking from different sides into the same place, we can see different changes of cityscape, four of them can be counted here.

Since this place of the town (mostly because of war) experienced obvious urban transformation, a wish occurs to look into this exploratory place from other observation angle (from A part of the Old town, beyond the river). As it could be seen from photo fixations (Fig. 23–26), a territory of recreational purpose currently exists instead of former layout. Biržos building was high enough, so it is possible to think, that this object was important in the cityscape and also as a guide.

In summarising noticed changes of part of the cityscape, exploratory point, from several directions of observation, it is possible to state, that three large objects and two smaller details disappeared within a century, as well as four new buildings of modern construction (three of them greatly changed the cityscape and became an identity of the town), a couple of new terrains of new functional purpose and several significant glassy details in old buildings occurred.

A space, earlier built with large and sufficiently high buildings, gradually (Fig. 27–28) became empty public space. Development of this place changed because of military actions, for which not only Biržos building but also Biržos Bridge suffered.

Bridge, as an engineering building, had to be rebuilt as soon as possible for natural reasons of communication with a part of the town on the other side of the river. Politicians of the town more

Fig. 23–24

Biržos building in 1914 and the same place in 2012 (prepared using interactive maps and information from thematic forums)

Fig. 25–26

Layout of Danė (Dangė) riverside during different periods (prepared using interactive maps and information from thematic forums)

loudly discuss about development of current plaza. They want to build a building of administrative purpose in this place. Certainly, it will be glassy neologism, but it's difficult to decide because of highness and influence of cityscape.

Returning to part A of Klaipėda Old town and searching for clear urban transformations in cityscape we must mention an object, defect of which was noticed earlier (Fig. 11–12). That is St. John's Church (Fig. 29), instead of which today only green space remained (Fig. 30).

As it was mentioned earlier, we all understand value and protected heritage differently. I. Alistratovaitė in her publication about development of urban visual image and protection under globalisation conditions (...2006) shall review significance of high buildings to the cityscape and states that high buildings in the world are built at the approaches to historical part of the town or in the central part, but it depends on particular country. Construction of high buildings in America's cities and towns has a tendency to expand all over the territory of the city (New York, Chicago). High construction in Asia in central part of the city or town is also not avoided, besides here it is mostly used for expression of rapidly growing economics, its rates, goals, where often deliberately

Fig. 27–28

January of 1945. Remains of Biržos building and germs of public space (prepared using the information from thematic forums)

Fig. 29–30

St John's Church in 1930 and in its place in 2012 (prepared using digital maps and information from thematic forums)

conditions are concluded for conclusion of contrast between different firms, their buildings (Shanghai, Hong Kong, Tokyo, Kuala Lumpur). In Europe a tendency to build high buildings at the approaches shall dominate i.e. protecting historical part of the town or city from aggressive development. Vertical buildings, occurring in European towns and cities, usually signify particular limit, therefore they are often named as signs, indicating divide of the old and new town centres (Berlin, Paris, Warsaw, Vilnius).

Remained (current) Old town of Klaipėda shall retain highness of its buildings, but high buildings already rush to alongside existing urban structure. Therefore, it is possible to state, that this is a standard of European extent, when divide of the old and new towns is signified.

Identity, sort of sameness, whole of human and thing's features, according to which it shall be recognised and distinguished among others – “a visit card”. Also the cityscape contains details, which are sort of identity, object or terrain for corresponding city, according to which we shall recognise the city and describe by its functional meaning, for example: Eiffel Tower – Paris; Žalgiris Arena – Kaunas; port, sailing vessel “Meridianas” - Klaipėda. From provided examples, significance of this identity to different extent shall be felt. Some objects are known to worldwide – international extent and the other are objects of local significance.

Objects of cultural heritage may be considered as identity of cityscape, if they shall be properly introduced to society and not hidden or left for disappearance. In case of Klaipėda, high building signifying the division between old town and new town, has already become particular identity of the city to Lithuanian extent because of its specific architecture. This building in Klaipėda cityscape can be seen from all sides and has important social and economical significance.

1 In summarising all archaeological literature about Klaipėda Old town, collected for this article, it is apparent that the city was influenced by different cultures, experienced many significant fires and military attacks. Although doubts for place of existence of the first old town still exist, but implementing regular development (usage) of current old town it was offered to divide it into three parts and develop them differently.

2 Parts A and B of Klaipėda Old town must be protected from wish of architects to realise artistic ideas for construction of new and modern buildings. Unfortunately, this space of cultural heritage is already damaged. C part of the Old town is an ideal space for creation. This place really lacks of initiative of architects in the construction of bright objects and buildings, which may become visible in cityscape or even can become an identity of this city. It is necessary to strengthen management of immovable cultural heritage by restricting lawlessness of architects when changing features of remained old town.

3 Comparison of facts, performed during researches, just confirms that Klaipėda Old town (Part A) shall correspond to ideal urban visions and schemes of ancient Romans, Renaissance

Conclusions

philosophers and planners. Remained system of streets and names of the streets shall confirm that. Ratio of city's length and width as well as even layout of functional zones in the city;

4 It is possible to envisage philosophical ideology, experiences and spiritual endeavours into self-realisation of corresponding personalities in urban structure (forms) of town, so it is necessary to retain parts A and B of Klaipėda Old town unchanged as longer as possible. In these parts buildings must be renewed only by aesthetically retaining primary features. It would be purposeful to insert neologisms in part C, which would have positive influence on cityscape and increase social as well as economical benefit for the town.

5 Expansion of Klaipėda city's primary development forced to change even flow of riverbed and it is very important detail in cityscape. Calculating changes in cityscape of this part of the Old town (A and C) we can make a conclusion, that the old cityscape is influenced by modern constructions, but highness shall remain unchanged. Some vivid buildings disappeared. Lack of especially significant objects of cultural heritage in cityscape is felt because of disappearance of two buildings, and 3 new buildings not only influence cityscape of Klaipėda, but also shall become identities of this city.

6 It is necessary to refresh Old town, so that this place would be visited by citizens not only during town events but daily. It is necessary to arrange Danė bank so that residents could feel access to water, as water give good emotions to residents. It is not necessary to build new buildings but to use the old ones invoking multifunctional services. Also there is a need to rebuild castle place, which would become an identity of the city and would spice up the cityscape by large object of cultural heritage.

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